

A RARE FORM HISTIOCYTIC DISORDERS OF THE LUNG: ADULT NIEMANN PICK DISEASE TYPE B

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ABSTRACT Although pulmonary involvement in Niemann-Pick disease is common, the appearance of interstitial lung disease in adulthood is rare. The differential diagnosis of adult-type Niemann-Pick disease includes pulmonary histiocytic disorders. We reported a 21-year-old man with a family history of Niemann-Pick disease type B and hepatosplenomegaly and a miliary appearance on chest X-ray suspicious of tuberculosis. The clinical, laboratory and radiologic data of our case were discussed.

KEYWORDS Niemann-Pick, histiocytic disorders, lung, lipoid pneumonia

Introduction

Histiocytes are a group of immune cells that include macrophages and dendritic cells. They play critical roles in inflammatory and phagocytic processes. Evaluation of morphological features and localization of the macrophages in lung biopsies may provide diagnostic clues for histopathological differential diagnosis of interstitial lung diseases [1]. Pulmonary histiocytic disorders are characterized by infiltration of alveoli and the interstitium by histiocytes. Histiocytic lung disorders include a broad spectrum of diseases, including primary disorders such as pulmonary Langerhans cell histiocytosis, Erdheim-Chester disease and Rosai-Dorfman disease and secondary disorders such as Niemann-Pick, Gaucher, Fabry and Whipple diseases. The lung can be affected alone or together with other organs [2]. Here, we report a case of adult Niemann-Pick disease type B involving clinical lung finding resembling miliary tuberculosis.

Case report

A 21-year-old man was admitted to our hospital with a history of hemoptysis and miliary appearance on chest X-ray suspi-

cious of tuberculosis. He had a smoking history of 4 years and smoked synthetic cannabinoids for two years. He was a pigeon breeder. The physical examination of the patient revealed coarse rales. High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) findings showed interlobular septal thickening and ground-glass opacity in the lower zone (Figure 1). Tuberculosis and hypersensitivity pneumonitis were added to the differential diagnosis. Sputum ARB, Xpert, e7 pigeon dropping antigen, anti-glomerular basal membrane antigen, serum IgE, ACE, and galactomannan in serum and urine Ca were negative. Pulmonary function tests were within the normal range: FVC% 85, FEV1% 91, FEV1/FVC 91, DLCO 78, DLCO/VA 89 and low diffusing capacity of carbon monoxide (DLCO) (Figure 2). PPD skin test was negative. Bronchoscopy was performed. Flexible bronchoscopy with transbronchial biopsy was not diagnostic. Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid was clear in appearance with 3% lymphocytes, 2% monocytes and 90% granulocytes. Lavage cytology showed numerous histiocytes with vacuolated cytoplasm (Figure 3). The multidisciplinary interstitial council suggested open lung biopsy for the patient. Open lung biopsies were taken from the right upper, middle and lower lobes. Histopathologic examination revealed endogenous lipoid pneumonia with alveoli and bronchioles filled with abundant finely vacuolated foamy macrophages (Figure 4). Foamy macrophages were negative for CD1a and s100 protein and were positive for CD68. There was no inflammation or fibrosis in the interstitium. Ciliated epithelial cells within airway walls showed vacuolation similar to that of histiocytes in alveoli (Figure 5). The histological findings were consistent with diffuse histiocytosis, suggesting Niemann-Pick disease type B.

The patient was investigated for Niemann-Pick disease. The

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Fig.1. Interlobular septal thickening and ground-glass opacity

acid sphingomyelinase level was 1,03 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{hour}/\text{lt}$ (reference range $>2 \mu\text{mol}/\text{hour}/\text{lt}$). BAL high-density lipoprotein C (HDL-C) level was <3 , lower than normal. The serum LDH level was 339 U/L (reference range 125-220 U/L). Family history was available for Niemann-Pick disease. The patient's family history included two sisters with NPD type B. One sister died at three years of age. The other sister was 17 years old. She was diagnosed with Niemann-Pick disease type B. The mother and father of our patient were related. Extrapulmonary involvement was investigated. EKG, echocardiography and cardiac magnetic resonance imaging were normal. Liver function was completely normal. However, hepatosplenomegaly was observed by abdominal ultrasonography. The neurological examination was normal.

The patient was being advised to stop smoking and using cannabinoids. No therapy has yet been undertaken. He was followed for eight months and remained stable.

Discussion

Pulmonary involvement by metabolic diseases is well described in disorders such as Gaucher disease, Niemann-Pick disease, Fabry disease and Hermansky-Pudlak disease. Nevertheless, extrapulmonary involvement is generally diagnostic in metabolic diseases. A lung biopsy is not necessary for diagnosis. Diagnosis is usually made by extrapulmonary disease. Metabolic diseases can arise in adults in association with respiratory symptoms. Gaucher disease is an autosomal recessive lipid storage disorder. Deficiency of glucocerebrosidase causes accumulation of lipid-laden macrophages (Gaucher cells) in various organs. There is a desquamative interstitial pneumonia pattern composed of intra-alveolar Gaucher cells. Lung involvement is uncommon and is usually present only in severe systemic disease. Fabry disease is an X-linked lysosomal storage disorder involving α -galactosidase. A deficiency results in accumulation of glycosphingolipids throughout the body. Cardiac involvement is frequent and is the usual cause of death in Fabry disease [1-3].

Fig.2. Pulmonary function reports show the low diffusing capacity of carbon monoxide (DLCO)

Fig.3. Numerous histiocytes with vacuolated cytoplasm in lavage cytology (Giemsa x1000)

Fig.4. Foamy macrophages in alveoli (HEx400)

Fig.5. Vacuolation in ciliated epithelial cells within airway walls (HEx400)

Niemann-Pick disease is an autosomal recessive lipid storage disorder. Sphingomyelin is a major component of cell membranes and myelin sheaths. Deficiency or absence of acid sphingomyelinase (ASM) activity causes lipid storage within lysosomes. There are membrane abnormalities including abnormalities in cell signalling pathways, receptor function and transport mechanisms. Sphingomyelin and cholesterol have strong interactions. Sphingomyelin is the primary accumulating lipid in Niemann-Pick disease types A and B. However, secondary abnormalities in cholesterol metabolism lead to dyslipidemia. Elevated total and LDL cholesterol and reduced HDL cholesterol have been observed [4]. Serum LDH level in our case was high. BAL HDL-C level was lower than normal.

The histopathological differential diagnosis our case included other metabolic disorders, cannabinoid used and primary histiocytic disorders. The spleen, liver and lung are the primary organ systems affected in all ASM-deficient patients. Phagocytosis and other biological properties are defective. These situations cause foam cell morphology. Foam cells known as NPD cells are readily detected in affected organs, as in our case [5].

Our patient smoked synthetic cannabinoids. Cell cytology of the BAL in cannabinoid users demonstrate numerous macrophages containing a refractile brown pigment [6]. Histiocytes in the lung of our patient did not contain brown pigment.

Although the diagnosis of type A NPD patients is usually established in childhood, the disease may rarely present in adulthood. Niemann-Pick C disease (NP-C) is a neurovisceral atypical lysosomal lipid storage disorder with rare adult onset as a chronic neurodegenerative disease [7]. The most common adult type NPD is type B with pulmonary involvement [8]. The differential diagnosis includes other histiocytic disorders. Pulmonary Langerhans cell histiocytosis is characterized by Langerhans cells with typical convoluted nuclear appearance. Langerhans cells are positive for CD1a and Langerin. Histiocytes in our case were negative for CD1a. Pulmonary infiltrates in Erdheim-Chester disease occur in interlobular septa, peribronchovascular spaces and the subpleural interstitium. Histiocytes in Erdheim-Chester disease do not contain nuclear folding and are negative for CD1a and Langerin. Rosai-Dorfman disease is a rare nonneoplastic proliferation of histiocytes with hematologic disorders. Infiltrates of Rosai-Dorfman disease consist of histiocytes with pale eosinophilic cytoplasm against a background of scattered lymphocytes and plasma cells [1]. Our patient did not have lymphocytes or plasma cells.

The most common clinical characteristics of the NPD are hepatosplenomegaly and mild to moderate dyspnea. Pulmonary involvement is bilateral. HRCT findings in NPD are interlobular septal thickening, ground-glass opacities, intralobular lines, and a crazy-paving pattern. Interlobular septal thickening and ground-glass opacities are most common the HRCT findings, as in our patient [9]. Pulmonary function tests in Niemann-Pick disease usually reveal normal lung volumes with a decreased diffusion capacity for carbon monoxide (DLCO), as in our patient [4]. Haematological, bone-marrow and hepatic abnormalities accompany NPD. NPD may be associated with myositis ossificans and alveolar proteinosis [10-12]. The diagnosis can be made by clinical history, radiological findings and laboratory studies. The diagnosis can be confirmed by findings on biopsy of various sites characterized by the accumulation of finely vacuolated, foamy, lipid-filled macrophages.

There is no treatment specific for pulmonary involvement by Niemann-Pick disease type B. Whole-lung lavage has been

suggested as a potentially useful treatment modality for patients with pulmonary involvement [13].

Conclusion

Pulmonary involvement in metabolic diseases such as Niemann-Pick disease can be observed in adults. Careful morphological evaluation of the features and localization of macrophages in the lung is often helpful to develop a differential diagnosis for adult Type B Niemann-Pick disease.

Conflict of interest

None

Funds

None

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